

Migration from private to public institutions: A phenomenological study on transitional challenges from teachers' viewpoints

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ABSTRACT

The migration of teachers from private schools to public schools is inevitable. The study described the transitional challenges experienced by the teachers as they migrated from teaching in private to public institutions. This study utilized the qualitative approach in collecting data, specifically, a Phenomenology methodology that influenced the research process that describes the lived experienced the seven (7) migrant teachers. The 7 teachers taught in private schools for a minimum of five (5) years before migrating to public schools. An in-depth interview guided by an aide-memoire was used to evoke the translational challenges experienced by the teachers. The analysis revealed the three themes emerged that generally describe the experiences of migrated teachers, these are *STOP*: an unapproachable step to colleagues, *LOOK*: the scarcity of the facilities in the school environment, and *LISTEN*: a walk the talk approach of the principal. Given the findings, the recommendation was anchored to the ideal circumstances of the migrated teachers in terms of colleagues, school environment, and principal.

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INTRODUCTION

Change in the working environment is one of the hardest decisions teachers can make in their teaching lives. Teachers before deciding to transfer to other institutions they have invested an emotional connection to their previous colleagues that makes it hard for them to leave. NCES (1995) mentioned that the movement of teachers between schools is called migration. The migration of teachers from private institutions to public institutions is inevitable. Teachers tend to shift from private to public for different reasons such as security of tenure, compensation, and the benefits they might get in a government-owned school. According to the report of Hernando-Malipot (2018), DepEd Secretary Leonor Briones expressed her concern about the significantly growing migration of teachers from private schools to public schools. Moreover, the DepEd Secretary noted that this growing phenomenon will lead to the closing of the small private school due to lack of enrollees as well as teachers. Though public schools offer substantial wages among teachers it is not deniably migrated teachers undergone a distinct adjustment in the new workplace. Migrated teachers experience challenges when relocating from private schools to public schools. In fact, Kim & Roth (2011), mentioned that the school setting approaches in accessing work-related information and learning are probably different from one school to the other. Due to changes in the working environment, migrated teachers struggle to their initial year in their new work environment.

There are many advantages and disadvantages a teacher must consider when it comes to choosing which school to teach, public institution, or private institution. Higgins and Abowitz (2011), said that public school is an institution founded by the government. Moreover, public school was operating according to the laws and policies designated to public schools. On the other hand, private schools are owned by single or group of persons, and somehow part of their business. Undeniably, the two institutions differ in many ways, especially when it comes to the school environment, faculty, benefits, and school leader. In terms of salary, public schools get higher and substantial pay compared to their counterpart. Meador (2019), mentioned also that the public school teacher typically paid more compared to private school teachers because most of the private schools do not have a teacher's union that will fight for a substantial salary. However, in terms of facilities, it is evident that private schools won the race.

With the incessant increase of teachers migrates from private schools to public schools, this study sought to describe the transitional challenges experienced by these teachers. In support of the current study, Hernando-Malipot (2018) reported that the migration of teachers from private to public school is the problem not only in the basic education system but as well in the higher education. Moreover, it has been reported by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) as a phenomenon. With the newly created faculty items in State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and the Department of Education (DepEd) many faculty in the private institution are leaving. For this reason, the focus of this study is to describe the challenges experiences of the transitional teachers from private schools to public schools in terms of the relationship with the colleagues, school environment, and leadership style of the school principal.

OBJECTIVES

The main focus of the study is to describe the transitional challenges experienced by the teachers as they migrated from teaching in private to public school institutions. Specifically, it will try to answer the following sub-questions:

1. How do migrated teachers describe their experiences with the following?
 - a. Relationship with the colleagues;
 - b. School environment; and
 - c. Leadership styles of School Principal.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Relationship with the colleague

Teachers act as the pillar of an organization that builds a sturdy nation. They deliver substantial knowledge and values needed by the students. With the support and collaboration with the school administrators, the success of the institution will be achieved. With this, it requires a good relationship among the teachers working in the organization. Herzberg (1966) as cited by Buljubasic (2008), defined relationships with peers as the social and working transactions with others on the job. Likewise, (House, Positive, & at, n.d.; Obakpolo, 2015), defined relationship at work as day to day interaction with colleagues, managers, and employees that involves mutuality. According to Ahmed (2019), the relationship of a teacher with their colleagues is important. He also added a positive relation among teachers to promote a knowledge-sharing culture in the school. In the same disposition, Professional, Drive, & Performance (n.d.) stressed out that if the workplace has a good strong relationship, care, support, and encouragement for one another are visible in the place. Moreover, Tallia et al. (2006) mentioned that people in a trusting relationship find input from one another and actually use or apply it. However, according to Professional, Drive, & Performance (n.d.) work place with weak professional relationship lessened the capacity for innovation and disengagement of some employees to the organization. The colleagues that compare their workload, working environment, resources, and opportunities in the workplace can create a difficult working relationship and communication between colleagues. In this study, the lived experience of the migrant teachers in terms of relationship with the colleagues will be described to know the transitional challenges they have experienced.

School Environment

Espelage et al., (2014) mentioned that the school environment is a general term that covers features of school climate or culture. According to Moore (2012), positive school environment contained the following components: (1) administration that is supportive, (2) rules enforced by the principal and teachers, (3) shared beliefs and values, (4) the communication among principal and teachers, (5) staff cooperation, (6) principal recognize the achievement and hard work of staff, (7) satisfaction with salary, and (8) knowing the school is well run. Likewise, Bawa (2015), emphasized that teachers are more fulfilled and stay longer in a positive working environment. Furthermore, he stressed that the school environment that matters most to teachers is the clean and well-maintained facilities that include accessibility of modern instructional technology. The study of Adesoji & Olatunbosun (2008), highlighted that the school environment together with teacher factors positively influences the achievement of the students. They also said that the school environment in terms of facilities, such as laboratory adequacy enhances the understanding, performance, and achievement of the students in chemistry class. However, in the study of Kigenyi et al. (2017), they found out that a poor school environment contributes to the poor performance of the teachers. At the equilibrium of the above statements on school environment and teacher performance, Kuncoro & Dardiri (2017), exposed in their study that there is no correlation between the work environment and the teacher performance. Furthermore, they said that the work environment includes that describe its physical conditions, psychological, and physical work environment does not directly support the performance of the teacher. Thus, a school environment that is clean, free from disturbance such as noise, with proper ventilation and lighting is undeniable will give teachers a good spirit to accomplish their tasks.

School Principal and its Leadership

The leadership of the principal plays a crucial role in motivating the teachers to perform their duty efficiently and effectively. It is a driving force in the leadership of the school principal to lead effectively to reach the common goals of the organization. Abdullah et al. (2018), said that teachers were motivated by the principal to carry their duties at school. Likewise, Gallmeier (1992) mentioned that the good managerial and leadership skills of principals are significant in motivating the teachers. Also, improving the teacher's motivation is an endless concern of the school principal. Thus, the motivation of the teachers towards their attitude on work varies on the leadership style

of the principal. However, according to Sujak (2010), as cited by (Due et al., 2020), leadership is the exercise of authority and influence of leaders over another person in order to accomplish the task.

According to Eboka (2016), leadership style is the different pattern of behaviors of the principal in the process of directing the teachers in achieving the shared goals. Hickman (2017), cited that there is various leadership style, namely: authoritarian leadership, laissez-faire leadership, democratic leadership, instructional leadership, transactional leadership, transformational leadership, situational leadership, and servant leadership that influences the teacher's motivation in their workplace. The authoritarian, also known as autocratic leadership as defined by Hickman (2017), is a leadership style that dictates and controls the organization in doing tasks. However, he added that democratic leadership is a style that is based on reciprocal and collaboration on principals and teachers. Thus, this leadership style is also known as participative. Abdullah et al., (2018), define transformational leadership as establishing a self-engagement of value sharing that motivates the whole school community to reach the shared goals. Furthermore, Cohen (2015) defined laissez-faire as no leadership, since subordinates work without thorough guidance from the leaders. He also expressed that transactional leadership is more on reinforcement or discipline, depending on the performance of the teachers. While according to Hickman (2017), situational leadership is the style of the leader that adapts to the behavior of followers. It is based on the willingness and ability of the subordinate to accomplish a certain task. He also defines servant leadership as leaders that commit themselves to build better organizations and ultimately creating a fairer and more caring workplace. Essentially, these leadership styles contribute to the success or downfall of the organization. Consequently, Hickman (2017), speculated that the satisfaction of teachers directly relied on the relationship with their leader. With this, the current study will describe the relationship experiences of the teachers who migrated from private schools to public schools to the leadership style of their previous and current principal.

Phenomenology Study

Creswell (1999) describes the phenomenology as a study that describes the meaning of lived experiences of a phenomenon of several individuals. Similarly, Creswell et al. (2007) also mentioned phenomenological study describes that all the participants have in common as they experience a certain phenomenon. Moreover, he discussed that the phenomenologist works much on from the specific statements of the participants. According to Starks & Trinidad (2007), phenomenology study is interested in the common features of the lived experience of the individuals. They added that the typical sample sizes for phenomenological studies range from 1 to 10 persons. They believe that few individuals that experience the phenomenon and can provide detailed information on their experience might suffice the uncovering of its core elements. In this study, the lived experience of the migrated teachers from private schools to public schools will describe the challenges they experience in terms of the relationship with the colleagues, school environment, and leadership style of the principal.

METHODS

This study utilized the qualitative approach in collecting data to draw answers from the presented research problems. Specifically, Phenomenology methodology influenced the research process. According to Creswell et al., (2007), phenomenology describes the common experiences of the participants in a phenomenon. It reduces the experiences of individuals with a phenomenon to a description of the universal essence. Accordingly, Moustakas (1994) as cited by Creswell et al., (2007) and Dela Fuente (2021) mentioned that phenomenology describes the lived experience of individual and arrive at the description of the essence of these experience without doing analyses or explanations. The summary of the full research process is presented in the table below.

Table 1. Summary of research process

Phenomenology Process	Participants	Data Collection / Instrument	Data Analysis
Phase 1: Preliminaries			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing of interview questionnaire (aide memoire) • Securing permits from the office of the School Principal. • Securing of informed consent form 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts in the fields • School principal • 7 Teachers from Private School Migrated to Public School 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview questionnaire (Aide memoire) • Informed consent form • School permit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coding of suggestions from the descriptive content validation of experts.
Phase 2: Data Gathering			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants were interview • The participants describe their experiences in terms of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Relationship with the colleagues (b) School environment (c) Leadership style of the principal • The researcher recorded and took notes of the interview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 Teachers from Private School Migrated to Public School 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview questionnaire (Aide memoire) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recording and coding of teacher's experiences • Interview transcriptions
Phase 3: Post Data Gathering			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The researcher transcribed the recorded interview • The researcher highlighted the significant statements, sentences, or quotes that yield understanding of the experience. • The participants validated and signed the transcriptions of the interview • The researcher developed clusters of meaning from the significant statements into themes • The researcher wrote description of the participant experienced based from the significant statements and themes • The researcher wrote description of the context or 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher • 7 Teachers from Private School Migrated to Public School 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recorded interview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transcribing the recorded interview • Highlighting the significant statements, sentences or quotes • Validation and signing of the transcription by the participants • Formulating of themes from the clusters of meaning of the significant statements • Textural description • Structural description • Writing a composites description that presents the essence of the phenomenon

setting that influenced the participants experience

- The researcher describe the essence of the timing experience

Participants

Using purposive sampling, seven (7) participants were chosen from the different public schools. The seven participants were the teachers taught in a private school for a minimum of five years before transferring to a public school. The teachers were purposively selected that provide detailed information on the phenomenon that is being studied.

Instrument

An in-depth interview with the participants was accomplished. The aide-memoire (guided interview questions) were used to allow further probing. The participants were interviewed for about an hour regarding their experiences in their previous institution (private school) and their current workplace (public school) in terms of the relationship with the colleagues, school environment, and leadership style of the principal. The interview as recorded using smartphones and was transcribed and analyzed.

Data Analysis

The research do the recording, transcribing, coding, thematizing, and analysing the qualitative data which was deduced from the interview with the participants during the research process as used by Dela Fuente (2019).

Ethical Consideration

Inform consent form was given to the migrated teachers to seek permission to interview them. During the interview, participants were informed of the research's purpose and that they could withdraw at any time, even in the middle of the interview, if they felt uneasy or changed their minds. Additionally, participants' anonymity and privacy were protected.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Thematized qualitative data gathered from the participants that probed the experience of teachers from private school to public school and the ideal workplace of the migrant teachers.

1. Teacher's experiences in private institution and public institutions.

In the study, participants' interview was thematized to explore the transitional challenges they experience in their change of station from private to public school.

Table 2. Experience with the colleagues

Themes	N	Excerpts Culled From Teacher's Interview
Intimidating	5	"Sometimes in the public-school many teachers are have very strong personality and they are very persuasive maybe they are very, or they have a very strong personality in giving their points of view"

		“Some of the teachers will try to intimidate other teachers in emphasizing what they want to tell about anything” (Teacher 1)
Work Oriented	2	<p>“when I transfer to public school iba yung dating sa akin, parang hindi ko nagagagawa yung dating ginagawa ko kapag after class, example sometimes after class we go to mall, manonood ng sine kasama yung mga kaibigan ko sa private school. Pero nung nagtransfer ako sa public parang nawala yun, kasi parang mas nakafocus sila sa ibang agenda”</p> <p><i>(When I transfer to public school it gives me other impression, I cannot do the things I usually do after class, example sometimes after class we go to mall, I watch movies with my friends in the private school. But when I transferred in the public school all of those happenings are gone, it is like they are more focus in other agenda)</i> (Teacher 2)</p>
Professionalism	2	<p>“(Private) the way the teachers interact during my teaching since in the private school we're very close most of us were very young... and also, pag may problem we really address to the administration”</p> <p><i>(Private) the way the teachers interact during my teaching since in the private school we're very close most of us were very young and also, if there is problem we really address to the administration”)</i></p> <p>“(Public) my faculty members are very much professional in terms of relationship as much as possible we don't entertain the negative thought pag may mga problems we just resolve it we just address the problem to our unit head which is the coordinator in the subject area”</p> <p><i>(Public) .my faculty members are very much professional in terms of relationship as much as possible we don't entertain the negative thought if there are problems we just resolve it we just address the problem to our unit head which is the coordinator in the subject area”)</i> (Teacher 3)</p>
Supportive	3	<p>“When I was working in a private school my former colleagues were very much willing to help me adjusting from being a student teacher to a full-time teacher”</p> <p>“when I entered the public school, my co teachers were nice and welcoming”</p> <p>“My co teachers in private and public school were both nice and very accommodating” (Teacher 4)</p>
Blabbermouth	2	<p>“Open kami sa isa’t isa, yung mga ideas namin nakakapagshare kami ng mga ideas na kahit bonding times pinag-uusapan pa din namin yung mga strategies”</p> <p>More on chismisan, madalas personal na chismis kahit na 3 years pa lang ako sa public school parang nasagap ko na yung mga personal chismis”</p> <p><i>(“We are open with each other, our ideas there are sharing of ideas even though it is our bonding times, we have conversation on different strategies”</i></p> <p><i>More on gossip, it is more on personal gossip, though it is only my 3rd year in public school, it is like I heard all the personal gossip”)</i> (Teacher 5)</p>

*N=Number of Teacher-Participant

As gathered from Table 2, the teacher themed their experiences with the colleagues into six (6). These colleague experiences are *intimidating*, *work-oriented*, *professional*, *supportive*, *blabbermouth*, and *monitoring*. As mentioned in the experience of the group under the *intimidating*, teachers from private schools when shifted to public school felt unsettled to their new colleagues because of the age or seniority in the service. This support the claim of Psychiatrists’ Support Service (n.d.), that the behavior of the senior is critical, undermining, and intimidating. *Blabbermouth* of the colleagues was experienced by some teachers who migrated to public school, they expressed their dismay because of the frequent gossip that is most of the time is more private circulating in their workplace. Meador (2018) stressed that gossip in the workplace is common, however, the school should be a haven. Additionally, he expressed that gossip is exasperating, it can separate the school’s faculty in half, and in the end, and the most affected are the students. Moreover, teachers experienced *work-oriented* colleagues in public because they are more concentrated on the different responsibilities in public school.

In the study of Ahmed (2019), mentioned that the unprofessional workload of teachers affects the social life of the teacher and causes them stress. Furthermore, *professionalism* was emphasized by the teachers as the appropriate way of solving the problems or conflicts when it arises in their work environment. This supports the claims of Sherpa (2018), which stated that the teachers should be affectionate and cautious in communicating so that solutions to the problems will be easily attended whenever problems and difficulties arise in the workplace. Lastly, teachers experienced a *supportive* colleague. Migrated teachers expressed their delight with their colleagues since most of them are supportive, welcoming, and very accommodating. Johnson (2006) mentioned that a supportive working condition enables teachers to be more effective, it enhances the quality of teachers and can improve retention.

Table 3. *Exposure to school environment*

Themes	N	Excerpts Culled From Teacher's Interview
Unavailability of facilities	5	“Challenges when you shift from private to public school, I think the facilities, the availability ng mga teaching devices” <i>(“Challenges when you shift from private to public school, I think the facilities, the availability of the teaching devices”)</i> (Teacher 5)
Maintenance of facilities	4	“In public, we dysfunctional chairs and when you have to request replacement or repair it takes time, but in private when we have a replacement or repair of facilities and they could do that within two or three days and you already have your chairs something like that” (Teacher 1)
Following Standards	4	“Honest to goodness we are following the ISO and then the standard operating procedure Kung saan napaka ideal namin at Sana lahat ng public school sumusunod sa standard operating procedure”. <i>(“Honest to goodness we are following the ISO and then the standard operating procedure wherein we are very ideal, and I hope all the public school should follow the standard operating procedure”.)</i> (Teacher 3)
Sufficient Facilities	2	“As I say before there's no difference in terms of facilities sa school ko dati talagang lahat prinoprovide may books may mga laboratories lahat kompleto dito since this is founded by the government wala masyadong problema this is Philippine Science High School the premier science High School in the country so ibig sabihin dito nilalaan lahat ng pondo ng government” <i>(“As I say before there's no difference in terms of facilities of my previous school, in which they are providing the books, there are laboratories, it is complete, here, since this is founded by the government there is not much problem, this is Philippine Science High School the premier science High School in the country, meaning the government are allocating the funds here.)</i> (Teacher 3)
Unventilated classroom	3	“the classroom sobrang init para bang wala halos hangin tapos napakaliit pa” <i>(“the classroom is extremely hot, like it almost has no air, then it is too small”.)</i> (Teacher 5)
Large Area	1	“Dito sa public sobrang luwang ng lugar na ito, kumpara sa kanila kasi sila para silang nakakakulong sa isang ano ehh, kumbaga sila limited yung galawan nila, yun lang” <i>(“Here in public the area is very large, compared to them, it is like they are in the cage, and they have limited space”.)</i> (Teacher 6)

*N=Number of Teacher-Participant

The exposure of migrated teachers to the school environment was themed in table 3. Generally, the experience of teachers was the *unavailability of facilities, maintenance of facilities, following standards, sufficient facilities, unventilated classrooms, and large areas*. The *unavailability of facilities* denotes that teacher experienced

insufficient or lacking facilities like projector, books, and other teaching devices. Also, they emphasized that some facilities were dysfunctional which opted them in providing their own facilities coming from their own pockets. *Maintenance of facilities* as experienced by the teachers is the action taken by the school in sustaining their school environment. Teachers stressed the length of waiting before fixing the dysfunctional facilities, cleaning the school environment, and proper use of the facilities, compared to their doings in private schools. The migrated teachers described their experience in an *unventilated classroom* as a hot room or room with no proper ventilation. This is another concern for teachers with a respiratory problem.

This aligns with the report of Hernando-Malipat (2019), who mentioned that it is the same old problems in the public school especially, every opening of the classes. She added that the shortage of facilities such as classrooms, and resources due to the incessant increase of students every year. She also noted that teachers and students are holding their classes in a deteriorating classroom with leaks and classrooms divided into two using plywood as a separator. Furthermore, it is also relative to the report of Alcober (2018), which mentioned that the Department of Education (DepEd) is experiencing insufficiencies in classrooms and learning materials, and the absence of electricity and water facilities in some areas. Consequently, migrated teachers expressed a positive outlook on the facilities in the public school. The migrated teachers described the *large area* as a spacious place of the public school compared to the limited area in private schools. Moreover, the *following standards* as explained by the teacher as strictly following the ISO and the standard operating procedure in utilizing and procuring the facilities. Lastly, *sufficient facilities* described as all the resources and laboratories are complete. Perhaps the schools belong to Philippine Science High School wherein the government allotted substantial funds for its operation.

Table 4. Cognizance on principal leadership

Themes	N	Excerpts culled from teacher’s interview
Communication	2	“Kung iisipin mo nasa office lang siya pero yung lahat ng problema,lahat ng magpapaganda, lahat ng pag aayos, lahat ng pakikipag usap sa ibat ibang klase ng mga tao sa kanya nag aano yun” (“If you notice, he stays only in the office but all the problems, all that can be enhanced, all the maintenance, all the communication to various people, he entertains those”.) (Teacher 6)
Work Efficiency	3	“So, they empathize with the teachers, usually in the private school where I taught” “In the public school, the school leader seems to focus more on the way you teach or the way you pass the requirements” (Teacher 1)
Teacher’s Development	6	“in public schools offer more training and seminars to teachers that helped them to be effective and efficient teachers. But somehow private schools also offer training to teachers but limited only” (Teacher 4)
Role Model	5	“... sa public-school leader namin yung pagiging ano nya ahhh outspoken at saka yung disciplinarian kasi luminis ang school namin nung bago na yung principal” (our public-school leader is his being outspoken and he is disciplinarian because our school became clean because of our new principal) (Teacher 2)
Task Delegation	2	“Principal in private school are very hands on in leading the preparation of teachers if there is an upcoming school program. While principal in public school give directions and instructions on how a particular school program should be done and leave the preparation to the hand of capable teachers. he usually assigns teams in particular task” (Teacher 4)
Unavailable	3	“yung relasyon namin sa private ko dati ok yung relasyon namin so igaguide kapa nya kung ano yung kulang mo sa pagtuturo paghandle ng mga estudyante so maaapproach kagad yung principal mo sa private school. Aah sa public school kase alam naman natin na ang mga principal ay busy sa mga seminars sa mga meetings sa

		ganito sa ganyan so mas madaling iapproach yung principal sa private school kesa sa public” (<i>Our relation in private, then our relation is okay, so he will guide you if there are lacking in your teaching, the way you handle students, so you can easily approach your principal in private school. Uhm, while in the public school, we know that principals are busy with seminars, meetings, like this or like that, so the principals in private school are more approachable compared to public</i>) (Teacher 7)
DepEd Order Driven	3	“In private school naman yung leadership qualities nila okay naman mas inaadmire ko yung pagiging optimistic” (<i>“In private school their leadership qualities are okay, I admire most is their being optimistic”</i>) “Sa Public sa ngayon wala akong inaadmire sa kanila sorry to say pero syempre sila yung principal namin kaya sumusunod na lang kami parang kumikilos sila base lagi sa memorandum na ipapadala sa kanila” (<i>“In public, sorry to say but I don’t admire as of the moment, still, since he is the principal that is why we are following him, it seems that they are doing actions base on the memorandum sent to him”</i>) (Teacher 5)
Parents	1	“Kasi pag nasa private school ka, parang alop ka sa principal mo, kasi siya ang boss mo talaga. Dito yung principal mo dito parang tatay o nanay mo lang din” (<i>When you are in the private school, you are cautious with your principal, because he is your boss. Here your principal is like your father or mother</i>) (Teacher 6)

Table 4 uncovers the themed on how the teachers’ cognized the leadership style of their principal. The theme emerged on the group were the *communication, work efficacy, teacher’s development, generous, role model, task delegation, unavailable, DepEd Order driven, and parents*. As mentioned in the comments of the groups under the *unavailable*, teachers expressed that their principals in public are always not around because of the different seminars and meetings they are attending and if they are in the school, the principal stay most of their time in their offices which do not give them time to approach them. Kelly (2019), stressed the importance of visibility of school principals to the welfare of the school staffs and students. Moreover, she emphasized that active listening skills must be learned and practiced by the school principal to build bridges between them. Hence, they must be highly visible and must be comfortable to approach and to interact. *Task delegation* was described by the teachers as an additional assignment to their initial workload. This could be a coordinator in a specific subject area or leader in a particular program of the school which is different when they are in the private school because as they mentioned private school principals were very hands-on in leading the preparation of the school programs. This affirms the statement of Hoff (2019), which stated that the leadership of the principal is distributed to its subordinates, which encourages cooperation and teamwork among colleagues. Thus, the colleagues feel more invested in the success and failures of the school goal. Moreover, the teachers expressed that their present principal as *DepEd Order driven*. They stressed that the leadership style and actions of their present principal are always based on the DepEd Order given to them. Furthermore, *work efficiency*, as described by the teachers is the efficiency of the principal to accomplish the school requirements for the school year. Thus, principals are more focused on complying with the school requirements.

The teachers conveyed that their present principal in the public-school displays their leadership during the teacher’s development. They mentioned that their principal is giving them training and seminars, and also, they were observed monthly. This supports the study of Dufrene (2018), they stressed that the principals may increase the capacity of their teachers by giving professional development like sending them to seminars to enhance their content or through constructive feedback during a classroom observation. The *role model* theme expressed that their principal is setting a good example to them that they may emulate. Quick (1997), revealed the significance of the moral role model amongst principals in creating and establishing climate, culture, and community that embodies the values they emulate. Additionally, the *communication* theme describes the formal or casual talk of the teachers and principal which is lacking. They expressed the lack of open communication with the principal since he is

always staying in the office. Manafa (2019), mentioned the importance of communication in the effective management of the school. He stressed that the usage of good communication in the organization augments the morale of the staff and make them more productive and significant in attaining the common goals of the school. Lastly, the principal exhibits of being *parents* to them. The teacher mentioned that his principal acts like their parents by giving them appropriate attention as parents do. Zheng, Shi, & Liu (2020) mentioned in their study that the combination of strong authority with fatherly benevolence is called a paternalistic style leadership. They also found in their study that this paternalistic leadership or parent-like leadership has a positive impact on the teacher’s commitment to their work.

Figure 1. Representation of Experiences

Structural Representation of Migrated Teacher’s Experiences

Through the descriptions of the participants, three themes emerged relative to the experiences of migrated teachers in public schools, in terms of their colleagues, school environment, and principal. Consequently, the researcher developed the Representation of Experiences, a conceptual model which represents the experiences of migrated teachers as they started to work in public school after teaching in private schools for several years (see Fig.1). This includes (1) STOP: an unapproachable step to colleagues, (2) LOOK: the scarcity of facilities in the school environment, and (3) LISTEN: a walk the talk approach of the principal.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, several experiences were raised by migrated teachers in terms of colleagues, school environment, and leadership style of principal. The proffered recommendations were anchored to the ideal circumstances of the participants.

Ideal colleagues

Teachers from private schools when transferred to public schools mostly experience intimidating and blabbermouth colleagues. It is highly recommended that migrated teachers should deal with this kind of professionalism. Correspondingly, teachers from public schools should also be cautious in their action – be a professional. As shared by the participant:

“Siguro relationship para maging maganda naman yung pagsasama and we are all teachers maging professional in all aspect para chillax lang. (*Perhaps the relationship in order to be good, and we are all teachers we should be professional in all aspect, so that it is chillax*)” (Teacher 5)

It was also recommended that the relationship with the colleagues should establish teamwork and attachment among the teachers to yield a functional and harmonious relationship. As mentioned by the participants:

“*madedescribe ko yung magandang samahan kung walang kompetisyon na nangyayare walang nagmamataas walang nagpapamukha sayo na ganito dapat ganyan dapat yung ginagawa isa din sa magandang samahan yung nagtutulungan katulad sa public. (I can describe an ideal relationship if there is no competition happening, no ego, no one will tell you that this is or that is the correct action, also an ideal relationship is there is teamwork.)*” (Teacher 6)

“*ang turing dapat isang pamilya lang kayo, kasi yung relationship dapat hindi mawawala although hindi kayo magkakakilala, hindi kayo magkakamag anak, hindi kayo magkakamukha ng gusto pero dahil nga nasa iisang iinstitusyon kayo dapat kung ano yung ikakaganda ng samahan na dapat na pakisama mo, yun yung ano. (the treatment should be like you are family, the relationship should not be taken for granted, though you do not know each other, you are not related, you have your likes, since you belong to the same institution, it should be what can be good for the relationship, you should do that)*” (Teacher 7)

Lastly, it was recommended that there is respect between colleagues. This is very essential in the workplace since teachers are also diverse and have their own beliefs. Respect in communicating and giving their point of view. As shared by the teachers:

“*With respect in terms of communication, in terms of having casual talks, there should always be a respect, that’s for me is the ideal relationship with the colleagues*” (Teacher 1)

Ideal school environment

The school environment of private is different from the environment of public schools. It is recommended that the school environment in public schools must be conducive, has complete facilities, has a spacious room, and has a clean environment. As mentioned by the migrated teachers:

For conducive room:

“*I believe that it should always be conducive to learning for both teachers and students so it should be prioritized that students should, well comforted and/or students could be able to have a very conducive learning, in terms of complete chairs, well ventilated classrooms, well maintained facilities so that teaching and learning process could be done in a smooth process*” (Teacher 1)

For complete facilities:

“*Okay lang kung maliit yung school pero mabigyan sana ng priority yung mga laboratory kasi kailangan na kailangan ng mga bata. Hindi natin kailangan ng puro visual aids sa pagtuturo, kailangan hands on para sa student (it is okay if the school is small, but the laboratories should be given priority, because it is the mostly needed by the students. We don’t always need the visual aids in teaching, hands on is more needed by the students)*” (Teacher 5)

For spacious room:

“Yung classroom malaki, so there is spacious space for learning, spacious din sya and I think facilities are very congruent for teaching and learning of the school. *(the classroom is big, so there is spacious space for learning, spacious and I think facilities are very congruent for teaching and learning of the school)*” (Teacher 3)

For clean environment:

“May playground, malinis ang kapaligiran *(there is playground, clean environment.)*” (Teacher 7)

Ideal principal leadership

The school principal is the captain of the ship. They sail with the teachers and the students to the wind and current goals of the institution. Moreover, they are the key in establishing a good school environment. It was recommended that the school principal in public should be sympathetic in dealing with the teachers, students, and stakeholders. They must have a heart in their subordinates. As mentioned by the teacher:

“Probably the consistency there must be precision as a school leader you must have heart to your subordinates” (Teacher 3)

It was also recommended principal should be enabler, approachable, and reasonable. As respectively mentioned by the participants:

“Yung gagayahin mo sya. Kasi diba kung ang principal mo ay tatamad tamad, eh tamad lang naman principal ko eh syempre gagayahin mo katamaran nya. Pero kapag nakikita ko na masigasig ang principal, responsable, kaw na bilang teacher mahihiya ka sa kanya. *(You can emulate him. When your principal is lazy, since your principal is lazy you will be going to be lazy as well. However, if you see your principal as hardworking, responsible, you as a teacher you will be cautious)*” (Teacher 7)

“Syempre kailangan professional in dealing with their teachers, very professional dealing with their student and also the parents of the students *(“Of course professional in dealing with their teachers, very professional dealing with their student and also the parents of the students)*” (Teacher 5)

I believe that a school leader should always be firm, strict, and fair in terms of having decisions, how to discipline their teachers, especially, in coming and ending the class time or attending school activities, it should always be fair and square to everyone” (Teacher 1)

Lastly, to reach the shared goals of the schools, it was recommended that the school principal is empowered leader, goal-oriented, and responsible. As respectively expressed by the participants:

“Ah sa tingin ko 50% na susunod sya sa deped sa mga rules and regulations nito at 50% din na makikinig sya sa mga colleagues nya sa eskwelahan. *(I think 50% they’re following DepEd rules and regulations and 50% they’re listening to his colleagues)*” (Teacher 6)

“An ideal principal is someone who has a clear vision of what he wanted to accomplish for the school” (Teacher 4)

“Ang ideal ay yung leadership talaga ay responsable. Kasi diba nga yung principal kapag responsable siya, at pag yung principal nyo gingawa nya yung bilang principal kaw na under

nya alam mo yun. (*The ideal leadership is responsible. If the principal is responsible, and if your principal is doing his job as the principal, as a subordinate you know that.*) (Teacher 7)

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